

Draft guide on access and benefit-sharing obligations for sampling and using fruit tree diversity

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ACRONYMS

- ABS : Access and Benefit-sharing
- CBD: Convention on Biological Diversity
- DDD : Due Diligence Declaration
- GR : Genetic resource
- IRCC: Internationally Recognised Certificate of Compliance
- ITPGRFA : International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture
- MAT : Mutually agreed Terms
- PIC : Prior Informed Consent
- sMTA: standard Material Transfer Agreement under the ITPGRFA
- TK: Traditional knowledge

Why this guide?

The FRUITDIV project aims to enhance the knowledge and use of crop wild relatives of the most important fruit species in human diets, which have originated in Europe and neighbouring regions, i.e. apples, apricots and cherries. It wishes to do so by collecting and gathering knowledge on these plants to adopt the most efficient conservation strategies, as well as facilitating the use of the most interesting traits and characteristics in breeding, especially for lower-input production conditions. It also wishes to carry out all of its activities in conformity with the complex regulations that surround the collection, movement and use of genetic resources, with great transparency and equity.

In this context, access and benefit sharing (ABS) legislation plays a central role to build solid foundations for the fair and equitable use of all genetic resources collected and researched during the course of the project, but also beyond. As ABS is an inherently complex topic, with important differences in policy approaches between States, even on the European continent, as well as important consequences in case of non-compliance, FRUITDIV's Task 1.5 is dedicated to track compliance with applicable ABS legislation.

This guide thus follows different objectives :

- to raise awareness and knowledge levels of FRUITDIV partners about the issue of ABS,
- to provide a step by step guide for FRUITDIV partners that are collecting genetic resources and/or using them in their research,
- to establish the internal FRUITDIV ABS compliance tracker system that will be managed by Task 1.5 leader.

The guide will be circulated to all partners, in addition to bilateral meetings with partners directly concerned with ABS legislation. It will be updated yearly to be presented at the annual meetings of the consortium to respond to the needs of partners, showcasing the issues that have arisen during the course of the project and the solutions brought forward.

1. What is Access and Benefit-sharing (ABS)?

ABS rules come from the principle that States have sovereign rights over the genetic resources found in their territory. They should therefore be able to control how those resources are used, and reap some of the benefits that derive from the use of these resources by researchers and product developers.

This principle has been incorporated into the [1992 Convention on Biodiversity](#) (Rio Earth Summit). Parties to the Convention (i.e. States that have ratified it) have decided to further develop the ABS rules by adopting the [Nagoya Protocol to the CBD](#), which entered into force on 01.10.2004.

As a result, researchers and product developers that **access genetic resources (GR) and the traditional knowledge (TK)** associated to these resources need **the prior informed consent (PIC)** of the country where the genetic resource has been collected. States may decide to not require PIC. When they do require PIC, the users of genetic resources should follow the national procedure to obtain an ‘ABS permit’, called an “**Internationally Recognised Certificate of Compliance**” (IRCC). When the State requires PIC, users should also sign a bilateral contract to determine **mutually agreed terms (MAT)**, which will establish different obligations, including those related to monetary and/or non-monetary benefit-sharing.

Even when they do not require PIC, all States that have ratified the Nagoya Protocol need to adopt **compliance and control measures** to make sure that the users of their country have complied with their ABS obligations, and obtained the PIC and MAT if needed.

Figure 1: General principles of ABS

The Nagoya Protocol is not the only international instrument dealing with access to genetic resources. In the agricultural field, the [2004 FAO International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture \(ITPGRFA\)](#) also deals with ABS, but takes a multilateral rather than a bilateral approach. Genetic resources that are part of the ITPGRFA's multilateral system can be accessed and used through a standard Material Transfer Agreement (sMTA) that has been developed by all participating States and must be used for all genetic resources falling under the scope of the ITPGRFA. The sMTA is considered as an IRCC. This means that if you have received the genetic resource with a sMTA, you simply need to comply with its content, and attach the same sMTA to the resource in all subsequent transfers. However, the ITPGRFA does not apply to all agricultural plant genetic resources, but only to those belonging to species listed in an Annex to the Treaty, which only includes *Malus* amongst the genera studied in FRUITDIV. The ITPGRFA will unfortunately not apply automatically to all *Malus* resources collected and used in the project, as genetic resources collected from the wild fall into a grey zone. As a result, all *Malus* collections need to also make sure which ABS measures are applied to the resources by competent authorities: bilateral Nagoya PIC-MAT, or the sMTA.

ABS documentation vs other permits related to genetic resources

When collecting genetic resources from the wild, researchers will need to obtain **additional permits that are not linked to ABS**. These permits are only concerned with the physical act of collection from the wild, and will depend on the legal status of the area where the genetic resources are collected from. For example, the collection of resources in protected areas will generally be subject to the issuance of a single permit, which will only look at the environmental impact of collection. These permits need to be obtained before any collection mission but do not generate benefit-sharing obligations, nor do they need to follow the subsequent uses of the genetic resources. On the other hand, ABS permits (or the internationally recognized certificates of compliance IRCC) will 'follow' through the subsequent chain of research on the genetic or biochemical composition of genetic resources. They need to be obtained only and only if the conditions listed below are met.

2. When do ABS obligations apply?

a. The country of origin/source has ratified the Nagoya Protocol

First and foremost, the **country where the genetic resource is collected or originates from needs to have signed and also ratified the Nagoya Protocol**. All the information related to the ratification status, with links to applicable national legislation can be found in the ABS Clearing-House ran by the CBD Secretariat : <https://absch.cbd.int/en/>

b. You are ‘using’ the genetic resource in the sense of the Protocol

The Nagoya Protocol does not apply to the simple physical collection of genetic resources, but rather when you ‘UTILISE’ genetic resources, i.e. when you “do research and development on their genetic or biochemical composition”. Only USERS of genetic resources, **private or public persons** who undertake **research or development on the genetic or biochemical composition of genetic resources**, will have ABS obligations (Article 2 of the Nagoya Protocol). The mere collection, transfer, cultivation or multiplication of genetic resources do not fall under the scope of the Protocol and will not generate ABS obligations.

What is NOT subject to ABS?

- Maintenance and management of a collection for conservation purposes, storage of resources or quality/phytopathology checks, verification of material upon acceptance.
- Identification of a genetic resource precedes utilization: Taxonomic identification or mere description of biological or genetic material, by morphological or molecular analysis, including through use of DNA sequencing, is not considered to constitute utilisation in the meaning of the EU ABS Regulation.

What is SUBJECT to ABS?

- If description or characterisation of a genetic resource is combined with research on that resource, i.e. the research is focused on discovery or examination of specific genetic and/or biochemical traits

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¹ These explanations are found in the Guidance document on the scope of application and core obligations of Regulation (EU) No 511/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the compliance measures for users from the Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from their Utilisation in the Union 2021/C 13/01, C/2020/8759, OJ C 13, 12.1.2021, available at https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv%3AOJ.C_.2021.013.01.0001.01.ENG&toc=OJ%3AC%3A2021%3A013%3ATOC

c. The country of origin/source has decided to regulate access to its genetic resources

Since the EU does not have sovereignty as a territorial entity, the **rules on ACCESS are determined at State level**. This is the same for non-EU countries.

Some States have decided not to regulate access to their genetic resources, by not requiring “prior informed consent”. In this scenario, there is no prior-authorisation procedure to follow, unless the species or the area where the collection is foreseen are protected or have specific rules applying to them (such as endemic species, wetlands or nature reserves). But these permits are not linked to ABS, and therefore do not imply the same obligations for users and will not be controlled/sanctioned in the same way.

Other countries have adopted specific legislation that requires users/collectors to obtain the authorities’ prior informed consent before ‘using’ the resource. In their national laws (or decrees), they determine how **‘USERS’** of genetic resources can **‘ACCESS’** them.

3. EU Legal Framework and General User Obligations

The **EU** as a legal entity has ratified the Nagoya Protocol, but rules on access to genetic resources remain with the sovereign rights of its Member States, which can each decide if and how to require PIC and MAT. Amongst the countries that are participating in the FRUITDIV project and where collection efforts will be carried out (both within and outside the EU), **only a handful have ratified the Protocol and have national procedures in place**. These are France, Greece, Romania and Spain. However, one must also be careful when using genetic resources that have been collected before the start of the project, making sure that adequate ABS documentation exists and follows all subsequent uses of the genetic resource.

Although there are no access rules at EU level, Regulation 511/2014² establishes quite strong **compliance and control measures**. No matter whether they require PIC and MAT on the resources under their sovereignty or not, EU Member States are obliged to control whether EU researchers and product developers have complied with ABS rules that have been adopted by third countries where the genetic resource used has been collected or originates from. ABS controls in the EU will thus check whether EU users have followed the national laws of the country that has ratified the Nagoya Protocol and established procedures for PIC and MAT, and where the genetic resource they are using originates from.

² Regulation (EU) No 511/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 April 2014 on compliance measures for users from the Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from their Utilization in the, *OJ L* 150, 20.5.2014, p. 59–71, available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32014R0511>

Figure 2: ABS legislation in the EU

Users of genetic resources in the EU have a **‘due diligence’ obligation** to seek and keep ABS-relevant documentation. In addition, users may have additional obligations that come from national laws, whether in EU or non-EU States (such as requiring a different document if the research gets closer to product development stage, or requiring all subsequent users to obtain separate permits).

There are **checkpoints** where ABS compliance is verified by competent public authorities, established at the reception of research funding and before the commercialization of a product.

A common web-based system called **DECLARE**³ has been established at EU level (except for Spain where a national system exists due to regional differences) to control ABS compliance at the stages of project funding and at product commercialization⁴.

³ Even though the use of the DECLARE system is not mandatory to submit due diligence declarations, it remains the easiest way to submit them electronically to the European Commission and also national competent authorities. A comprehensive user manual can be found at <https://circabc.europa.eu/ui/group/3f466d71-92a7-49eb-9c63-6cb0fadf29dc/library/03ade20f-c623-4c96-a4fe-6d71408cb76e/details?download=true>

⁴ https://sede.mapama.gob.es/porta/site/se/procedimientos-intermedio?theme_id=5

4. FRUITDIV ABS Compliance Tracker System

An ABS compliance tracking document will be developed and maintained by the **WP1.5 leader throughout the project as an ad hoc living Excel document available on the FRUITDIV Sharepoint** to follow the status of ABS compliance.

Each table line will correspond to a GR accession, containing some basic passport data (species/genus), the place and time of collection, information on the existence of ABS documents, including potential benefit-sharing obligations stemming from ABS permit.

- **FRUITDIV Unique Identifier**
 - to be able to work efficiently, each genetic resource will receive a unique identifier.
- **Other accession number (when it exists)**
 - if the GR has already been given an identifier or other number (like the NCBI number), please note it so that it's easier to track information that could exist on GR with relation to ABS.
- **IRCC identifier\number (when it exists)**
 - if an IRCC has been issued by a competent authority, its number should be indicated in the compliance tracker document.
- **Maintainer of accession**
 - specify the country and institution where accession is maintained/stored, if different than FRUITDIV partner, add institution name and country
- **Genus/Taxa/Species**
- **Date of collection/access (d/m/yyyy)**
 - date when GR/accession has been collected from site, if known or date when GR/accession has been transferred to FRUITDIV partner (from another partner or a gene bank for example). This can be the same date as the date of collection or not. If both dates are known, please note them both.
- **Country of access/origin**
 - country where the GR has been collected or country where the GR originates from. If the country of origin is not known, state the country where you received the accession from.
- **ABS Documentation**
 - this section will record whether the use of the resource falls under a contract, permit, international compliance certificate or material transfer agreement. If such documentation exists, upload the document on Sharepoint in the ABS-CH folder, with the unique identifier.
- **Conditions attached to the use of the GR**
 - this section will be filled out by the WP 6.1 task leader after examination of existing ABS Documentation, with a potential colour-coding mechanism to flag the potential restrictions and obligations that might stem from the use of the genetic resource (depending on the content of the material transfer agreements signed).

5. STEP-BY-STEP ABS Compliance Guide for FRUITDIV research partners

a. Establish if and how access to GR is regulated in the country where you have collected (or plan on collecting) plant material that you wish to 'use'

- Use the decision tree provided below and in Appendix 1 to determine your ABS obligations
 - Has the country signed and ratified the Nagoya Protocol?
 - Does the country require PIC *prior informed consent? *Check the ABS-CHM, websites of national authorities and scientific articles.*
 - What are the compliance control measures in your country? *Are there national checkpoints and rules on controls/inspections?*

Figure 3: ABS decision-tree (also found in Appendix I of this document)

b. Obtain ABS documents (PIC-MAT) from the country of origin\collection

If access to GR (and/or TK) is regulated in the country, you need to **contact the National Focal Point** to get a permit/authorization from the Competent National Authority (OBTAIN PIC/MAT), and follow the national procedure to obtain the authorization to use the genetic resource in the sense of the Nagoya Protocol and get all needed ABS documents. Contact details of your country's national focal point, as well as most (but not necessarily all) applicable legislation can be found in the ABS Clearing House website maintained by the CBD Secretariat : www.absch.cbd.int The FRUITDIV ABS task leader can assist you with the procedure if necessary.

In most ABS permit application procedures, authorities will require you to **describe the objectives of the project, as well as the different uses and transfers of genetic material**

foreseen within its scope, as well as **expected project outputs**. The following text can be used as a basis in this context:

The plant material will be used to make a phenotypic and genetic characterisation of crop wild relatives of European fruit tree diversity to enhance knowledge on these genetic resources, and ensure their conservation, both in situ and ex situ. The resources will notably be used for the development of nuclear populations of the different species collected, identifying the most interesting specimens in a conservation perspective, looking at representativeness and risk of genetic erosion. The individuals selected for the nuclear populations will be reproduced by seed and will form part of the collections that will be planted on the experimental farms of some of the project partners. The most interesting specimens will be studied more in depth to determine the most efficient ways in which they could be included in fruit tree plant breeding, especially in low-input and organic contexts. All project results will be published according to the European Union Horizon open-science policy principles. Information related to the origin of the resources, including ABS-related elements, will always accompany the resources, including any data that will be published in the framework of the FRUITDIV project. Meta- and genomic data linked to these genetic resources will be made available through a public database.

c. Fill out ABS relevant information on the passport data

Each FRUITDIV partner shall fill out information related to ABS compliance in the **passport data sheet** developed in WP1 and the database developed in WP.4, which will be echoed throughout the project.

This information gathering exercise needs to be done **for both existing and new accessions and should to at minima include** :

- Unique FRUITDIV Identifier
- Other Accession number (when it exists, for existing collections to be studied in FRUITDIV)
- Genus/taxa/species
- FRUITDIV partner maintaining the accession
 - Potentially also FRUITDIV partner to whom sample is transferred for phenotyping/genotyping
- Date of collection/access (d/m/yyyy, example 30/01/2024):
 - Date when GR/accession has been collected from site, if known or
 - Date when GR/accession has been transferred to FRUITDIV partner (from another partner or a gene bank for example). This can be the same date as the date of collection or not. If both dates are known, please note them both.
- Country of access/origin:
 - Country where the GR has been collected or country where the GR originates from. If the country of origin is not known, state the country where you received the accession from

d. Upload all ABS related documentation to ABS section of FRUITDIV Sharepoint

If **ABS documentation exists for the accession**, the FRUITDIV partner uploads the ABS document on the [FRUITDIV Sharepoint in the ABS-CH folder](#) under “WP1/Task 1.5 ABS-Nagoya” with the Unique Identifier in the document title under the format : “FRUITDIV.ABS.COUNTRY ACRONYM.PERMIT NUMBER” (for example, the first permit delivered by Spanish authorities would read FRUITDIVABSESP1).

This document could be an MTA, an international certificate of compliance (IRCC), a national permit or any other document issued by national authorities. If it is an IRCC, please indicate its number in the document title.

The ABS task leader will then fill out the FRUITDIV ABS Compliance Tracker with relevant information, and verify that it is echoed correctly in the main WP4 database.

Figure 4: Steps to be followed by FRUITDIV partners for ABS compliance (also found in Appendix II of this document)

e. Before using FRUITDIV material or transferring material to another partner or third party, check whether you can do so

Every partner using or transfer genetic material to another FRUITDIV partner or a third party needs to **make sure they are allowed to do so under the FRUITDIV ABS Compliance Tracker**, found in the project Sharepoint under “WP1/Task 1.5 ABS-Nagoya”.

If the tracker mentions that ABS obligations apply, the recipient of the material needs to be made aware of the restrictions surrounding the use of the material, especially if they are not part of the FRUITDIV project. In certain cases, the ABS permit needs to be forwarded to the third party (especially if it is an sMTA), in other cases, the national ABS authority will need to be contacted by the third party to receive their consent, and be issued another permit covering the research activities foreseen. *Transfers of genetic material to sub-contractors such as sequencing companies are allowed, provided that the MTA and general service contract specifies that none of the sequencing results may be used by the contractor or third parties.*

f. Comply with control measures established in your country

Genetic resource users based in the EU (except Spain) need to submit a **Due Diligence Declaration to the EU-DECLARE system**. A single declaration can be made by the project coordinator covering all the activities of the FRUITDIV project. Users established in Spain need to follow the national online procedure instead of DECLARE and provide authorities with the necessary documentation (ABS permit and ABS Compliance tracker described below).

If you are a genetic resource user based outside the EU and your country has ratified the Nagoya Protocol, then you need to follow the national procedure established in your country to control compliance with ABS obligations. *The FRUITDIV ABS task leader can assist you with the procedure if necessary.*

Appendix 1: ABS Decision Flow Chart

TK: Traditional knowledge
GR : Genetic resource

PIC : Prior Informed Consent
MAT : Mutually agreed Terms

DDD : Due diligence Declaration
NFP : National Focal Point

Appendix 2: Steps to be followed by FRUITDIV partners for ABS compliance

